

**FORMATION OF AN ALGORITHM FOR ORGANIZING THE PROCESS OF IMPORT
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Moscow Aviation Institute (National Research University), Moscow, Russia***Abstract**

This study is dedicated to the development of an algorithm for organizing the process of innovative import substitution in the aviation industry enterprise. The paper analyzes the main methods and approaches to import substitution in the context of the aviation industry, identifies the peculiarities of implementing innovative projects, and evaluates the effectiveness of using technologies and materials of national production instead of imported ones. The research includes an analysis of the current state of aviation industry enterprises, as well as methods and tools for implementing import substitution, allowing for the development of an algorithm for the successful implementation of the process of innovative import substitution in enterprises of this industry. The results of the study can significantly enhance the efficiency of managing the import substitution process and contribute to the growth of the competitiveness of the domestic aviation industry.

Keywords: aviation industry, aviation technology, competitiveness, import substitution strategy, import substitution program.

The aviation industry plays a crucial role in Russia's economy, influencing related sectors such as metallurgy, radio engineering, electrical engineering, and others. Moreover, it stands as one of the most scientific, technical, and innovative industries in Russia, driving the overall transition of the country's industrial complex to an innovative stage of development.

The aerospace sector involves the creation of fundamental types of aviation technology, such as airplanes and helicopters, and its classification into civil and military production. Currently, the aviation industry is in a transitional state. On one hand, it is actively evolving; on the other hand, production has not reached the scale typical of the 1990s. The main challenge for the aerospace industry in Russia is the dependence on foreign investors and suppliers of components that have not been produced in the country for an extended period.

The escalation of the situation in the global market, the imposition of sanctions against some Russian companies, the depreciation of the ruble due to changes in oil prices and the active growth of foreign currencies have had a negative impact on the Russian economy, emphasizing the country's dependence on external sources. In such a complex economic situation, one of the key strategies for the development and enhancement of competitiveness in the aerospace industry, both domestically and internationally, is the import substitution strategy. Additionally, the search for alternative sources of supply and the development of domestic production contribute to strengthening national security and reducing dependence on external suppliers.

The research topic on developing an algorithm for organizing the import substitution process in the aviation industry is relevant in the modern context for several reasons:

1. Economic aspect: Import substitution strategies are becoming increasingly crucial for ensuring economic stability and the independence of a state. In the face of global economic uncertainties and sanction pressures from unfriendly countries, the relevance of creating an effective import substitution algorithm in the aviation industry is extremely high.

2. Technological Progress: Technological advancements in the aviation industry are progressing rapidly, increasing the need for in-house production of key components and technological equipment. Therefore, effectively organizing the import substitution process can contribute to the development of domestic technological clusters.

3. Geopolitical Factors: Changes in global politics and international relations between countries can impact supply chains and dependency on foreign suppliers. Developing import substitution strategies in the aviation industry helps mitigate the influence of external geopolitical factors.

4. Industry Specifics: The aviation sector is characterized by a high degree of complexity and specific quality requirements for its products. Developing an algorithm to organize the process of innovative import substitution, taking these peculiarities into account, could enhance production efficiency and the competitiveness of enterprises.

Thus, research on this topic holds significant practical value and may lead to the development of specific strategies that contribute to the sustainability and growth of the aviation industry amidst contemporary challenges.

At the present moment, the strategy of import substitution in the Russian aircraft manufacturing sector is considered by the government as a priority direction for the advancement of a high-tech and science-intensive industry. However, the possibilities of this strategy, due

to the individual characteristics and features of the industry under consideration, cannot be fully realized without proper government support, including financial backing. Based on this fact, the Government of the Russian Federation has developed and approved the state program "Development of the Aviation Industry" [1].

The main objectives set for achievement by the program outlined above are as follows:

- Preservation of the status as a global aviation power;
- Modernization of the fleet of aviation products operating on the territory of the Russian Federation;
- Maintenance of scientific, technical, production, technological, and personnel potential at a level capable of ensuring the efficiency of aviation activities;
- Maintenance of the quality of aviation at a level capable of ensuring competitiveness in the global market;
- Development of international cooperation and expansion of the presence of national companies in the markets of aviation services and technology [2].

In the framework of this Program, a total of 107.9 billion rubles will be allocated to aviation industry and comprehensive support of the aviation sector in 2024–2026 in Russia. The goal is to achieve by 2030 a 50% and 90% share of Russian-made planes and helicopters in the fleets of major airlines, respectively. According to the director of the aviation industry department at the Ministry of Industry and Trade of Russia, by 2026 it is planned to increase the production of Russian-made planes, including MS-21, Sukhoi Superjet, Tu-214, and small aircraft LMS-901 "Baikal". The focus is on import substitution of key components. In August 2023, the prime minister of the Russian Federation announced about new measures to support domestic aviation production. Specifically, changes were made to the rules for providing federal budget subsidies for the production of mid-range passenger aircraft MS-21. These changes will allow aviation construction companies to receive about 20 billion rubles for technical modernization.

Also, in 2023, the program of subsidizing interest rates for loans obtained by companies for the purchase of Russian aviation equipment was extended. Additionally, according to a government decision, it will become easier to form a reservoir of spare parts: the amount of inventory will be determined based on the overall cost of equipment necessary for maintaining flightworthiness. [3]

On April 18, 2023, it was reported that the Russian Ministry of Industry and Trade (Minpromtorg) will allocate nearly 750 million rubles for the complete import substitution of engines for Sukhoi SuperJet aircraft and Kamov Ka-62 helicopters. Previously, Russian civil helicopters and aircraft used French engines PowerJet SaM146 and Turbomeca, but encountered issues due to sanctions. Therefore, a decision was made to modify domestic engines PD-8 and VK-1600. The tender for developing analogues of foreign components was completed in April 2023. [4]

According to data from the National Research University Higher School of Economics "Center for

Development," the implementation of the main provisions of the state aviation program shows a growth and development trend.

However, the high degree of dependence of the industry on government support creates significant difficulties in improving the aviation complex as a whole.

According to official data, at present, Russia has fully developed the military aviation sector, while civil aviation faces significant challenges. Due to this, the main measures aimed at developing a strategy of import substitution are focused on the civil aviation sector.

Analyzing the strategy of import substitution as a way to enhance the competitiveness of the Russian aviation industry, both domestically and globally, the following advantages can be noted:

- The government-led programs and measures aimed at reducing the actual proportion of imports in aviation production will significantly reduce the cost of components that were previously acquired from foreign companies. Establishing domestic production will reduce the average cost of the final product by 5–10%, which will enhance the competitiveness of products on the global market;

- The strategy of import substitution in the aviation sector is implemented under the direct control and support of the government, which allows aviation companies to reduce dependence on foreign investors, resulting in increased profitability of national products;

- Import substitution is associated with diversifying the economy, which means expanding the range of products by producing new ones. Thus, expanding the domestic aviation base will allow to release onto the global market products with unique characteristics, which will increase their consumer attractiveness;

- Developing domestic aviation in conjunction with the import substitution strategy will protect the domestic economy from the competitive influence of foreign groups through internal tariff and non-tariff regulation;

- Developing import substitution reduces the import of foreign-produced aviation products into Russia, which increases the attractiveness of domestic producers on the domestic economic market;

- Reducing the import of aviation products helps to change government policy towards the industry, which may lead to the development of tax benefits, lower prices for energy resources, reduced transportation costs, and changes in internal lending rates, resulting in a substantial reduction in production costs.

To successfully organize the process of import substitution while optimizing time and cost requirements, it is crucial to develop an algorithm that allows you to step by step determine what and in what sequence should be done. The algorithm for organizing the process of import substitution in the aviation industry includes several key steps:

1. Analysis of dependence on imports: determining the products or components that are usually imported to the plant. This may include studying suppliers, volumes of imports, and the reasons why these products/components are purchased abroad.

2. Assessment of local production opportunities: determining the possibilities for replacing imported

products or components through local production or supply from local suppliers. This may include analyzing technical capabilities, availability of necessary resources, and economic feasibility.

3. Developing an action plan: creating a specific action plan for replacing imports with local production or other methods. This plan may include stages such as finding local suppliers, modernizing production processes, developing new technologies, etc.

4. Gradual implementation: gradual implementation of the plan, step by step, to gradually replace imported goods or components with local production or alternative solutions.

5. Monitoring and evaluation of results: continuous monitoring of the replacement process to evaluate

the achieved results. This includes assessing the quality, effectiveness of production, economic benefits, and other factors.

6. Strategy adjustment: In case of necessity, adjusting the strategy based on the obtained data and experience.

This process requires close cooperation between various departments of the plant, including production, procurement, engineering, and strategic planning, to successfully implement import substitution and ensure the sustainability of production.

Figure 1 shows the procedure for formulating the strategy of import substitution in the aviation industry.

Fig. 1. Procedure for Developing an Import Substitution Strategy at an Aerospace Enterprise

Afterwards, it is necessary to formulate the algorithm for organizing the import substitution process at the enterprise. Figure 2 illustrates the algorithm for or-

ganizing the import substitution process at the enterprise, which can serve as the basis for implementing import substitution policies in aviation industry enterprises.

Fig. 2. Algorithm for organizing the import substitution process in the aviation industry enterprise.

In addition, it is necessary to ensure flexibility in the import substitution strategy for prompt adaptation to changes in the external environment. To ensure this flexibility, constant monitoring of its implementation is required. The control process, in turn, requires certain standards for monitoring. In the event of the need for correction, the import substitution strategy can be adapted. The proposed algorithm for implementing the

import substitution mechanism at the aviation enterprise level, with minimal changes, can be applied at the meso level. It can also serve as a basis for import substitution policies at the level of holdings and corporations. At the enterprise level in the aviation industry, the import substitution strategy can be implemented in various variations, and Figure 3 presents the most preferred options for its implementation.

Fig. 3. Proposed options for implementing import substitution strategy

The organization of the import substitution process at an enterprise is a complex, multi-component process that requires careful coordination of various stages. When developing an import substitution program, optimizing financial and time costs is an important stage. First and foremost, the enterprise must define its strategy for implementing the import substitution program before embarking on the development of the process execution algorithm. An efficient algorithm allows for sequentially determining the stages and their order of execution. This algorithm for organizing the import substitution process at the enterprise can serve as the basis for implementing import substitution policies in the aviation industry.

The development of import substitution strategy in the Russian Federation's aviation industry contributes to strengthening the competitiveness of domestic companies in the domestic market and stimulates the attractiveness of their products for export to the global market.

The study was supported by the Russian Science Foundation grant No. 23-28-10196, <https://rscf.ru/project/23-28-10196/>

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